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Fractions or kalāsavarṇa - Concepts in the Gaṇitasārasaṅgraha (G.S.S) of Mahāvīra Dr. P.M.Mini¹

Abstract

In ancient Indian mathematics we can see the idea of fractions and its operations. In Jaina works the discussion of fractions is made under the name Kalāsavarṇa. Different types of fractions are studied by Mahāvīra in G.S.S. He classified the fractions into 6 types with examples. The concept of unit fractions and their operations are also discussed in G.S.S. The unit fractions were discussed under the name rūpāmśakarāśī. These ideas of Mahāvīra can be utilised by the students of Mathematics for the better understanding of the concept of fractions

In ancient Indian mathematics we can see the idea of fractions and its operations. In Jaina works the discussion of fractions is made under the name Kalāsavarṇa. Kalā denoted the sixteenth part. So, Kalāsavarṇa literally means parts resembling $\frac{1}{16}$. So Kalāsavarṇa

come to signify fractions in general.

Different types of fractions are studied by Mahāvīra in G.S.S. v.3.54, p.106.² He classified the fractions into 6 types namely Simple fractions (Bhāga), Fractions of fractions (Prabhāga) Complex fractions (Bhāgabhāga), Fractions in association Bhāgānubandha Fractions in dissociation (Bhāgāpavāha), Fractions consisting of 2 or more of the above-mentioned fractions (Bhāgamātrā)

-
1. Assistant professor and Head, Dept. of Mathematics, M.A.M.O.College Mukkom
 2. Sri Mahaviracarya, sGanitasarasangraha translated by Dr.Padmavathamma, Siddhantakirthi Grandhamala, Hombuja 2000 v.3.54, p.106. भागप्रभागावध भागभागे भागानुबन्धः परिकीर्तितोऽतः । भागापवाहस्सह भागमात्रा षड्जातयोऽमुल कलासवर्णे ॥

Examples

1. Bhāga - simple fraction - $\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{4}$, etc.

2. Prabhāga - fraction of fractions - $\frac{1}{2}$ of $\frac{3}{4}, \frac{1}{4}$ of $\frac{2}{7}$, etc.

3. Bhāgabhāga - complex fractions

4. Bhāgānubandha-associated fractions.

5. Bhāgāpavāha - fractions in dissociation

6. Bhāgamātrā - Fractions consisting of 2 or more of the above-mentioned fractions.

When discussing about problems in different types of fractions Mahāvīra gives the method to find the numerators of certain fractions when its denominators and sum are given (G.S.S. v3.73 p114). Also, he gives the method to find the denominators of 2 fractions with given numerators and sum.

Another important contribution of Mahāvīra is the idea about unit fractions. The word used by him to represent unit fraction is 'rūpāmśaka rāśi'. He was very much interested in problems connected with unit fractions. Some examples are the following.

a. Mahāvīra gives the method to decompose a unit fraction into 2-unit fractions v 3.85, p 124.³

This sloka means that the denominator of the given sum multiplied by a chosen number is the denominator of one of the intended fractions and this denominator divided by the previously chosen number as lessened by one gives the other denominator, or factorise the given denominator and multiply one of these factors and the sum of the factors. This is the first required denominator. Similarly multiplying the other factor and the sum of the factors will give the second denominator.

ie., if $\frac{1}{n}$ is the given fraction $\frac{1}{n} = \frac{1}{np} + \frac{1}{\frac{np}{p-1}}$ where p is any

chosen quantity.

3. वाञ्छाहतयुतिहारश्छेदः स व्येकवाञ्छयाप्तोऽन्यः । फलहारहारलब्धे स्वयोगगुणिते हरौ वा स्तः ॥

$$\text{Or if } \frac{1}{n} = \frac{1}{ab}, b \geq 1 \text{ then } \frac{1}{n} = \frac{1}{a(a+b)} + \frac{1}{b(a+b)}.$$

- b. In G.S.S.v.3.78, p.119 Mahāvīra gives the method to decompose a unit fraction as the sum of fractions with given numerators:⁴

By this sloka, if $\frac{1}{n}$ is the sum of the given fractions and a, b, c, d

a r e t h e numerators then

$$\frac{1}{n} = \frac{a}{n(n+a)} + \frac{b}{(n+a)(n+a+b)} + \frac{c}{(n+a+b)(n+a+b+c)} + \frac{d}{d(n+a+b+c)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{R.H.S.} &= \frac{a(n+a+b) + bn}{n(n+a)(n+a+b)} + \frac{c+n+a+b}{(n+a+b)(n+a+b+c)} \\ &= \frac{a+b}{n(n+a+b)} + \frac{1}{n+a+b} \\ &= \frac{n+a+b}{n(n+a+b)} \\ &= \frac{1}{n} = \text{L.H.S.} \end{aligned}$$

So the result is true.

- c. In G.S.S. v.3.75, p.116 he also gives the expression for ‘1’ as the sum of ‘n’ unit fractions.⁵

As per the sloka if the sum of n unit fractions is one then the denominators of the fractions are $2 \times 1, 3, 3^2, 3^3, \dots, 3^{n-2}, 2 \times 3^{n-1}$

$$\text{ie., } 1 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3^3} + \dots + \frac{1}{3^{n-2}} + \frac{3}{2 \cdot 3^{n-1}}$$

4 लब्धहरः प्रथमस्यच्छेदः सस्वांशकोऽयमपरस्य । प्राक् स्वपरेण हतोऽन्त्यः स्वांशैकंशके योगे ॥

5 रूपांशकराशीनां रूपाद्यास्त्रिगुणिता हराः क्रमशः । द्विद्वित्यांशाभ्यास्तावादिमचरमौ फले रूपे ॥

d. Expression for '1' as the sum of '2n' unit fractions is given in G.S.S v.3.77, p.118⁶

This sloka states that if the sum of different unit fractions is 1 then the denominators are obtained by multiplying one integer (say n) and the next integer (n+1) and halving the product. The integer n can take values beginning from 2.

$$1 = \frac{1}{2.3. \frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{3.4. \frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{4.5. \frac{1}{2}} + \dots + \frac{1}{(2n-1)2n. \frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2n. \frac{1}{2}}$$

For finding the sum and difference of simple fraction the 1st step given by Mahāvīra is to make the denominators equal. The fractions of equal denominators can be added or subtracted by doing the operation for the numerators and putting the common denominator.

To make the denominators of fractions equal, Mahāvīra gives two different methods.

1. The first method is explained in G.S.S v.3.55, p.106⁷

This sloka means that in the operations relating to simple fractions multiply the numerator and denominator of the first fraction by the quotient obtained when the denominator of the second fraction is divided by the common factor of the denominators. Similarly multiply the numerator and denominator of the second by the quotient obtained when the denominator of the first fraction is divided by the common factor of the denominators.

2. The second method is 'method by using Niruddha (L.C.M)':- Mahāvīra introduced the word Niruddha means L.C.M in G.S.S. v.3.56, p.108⁸

As per the sloka niruddha is obtained by means of the continued multiplication of all the common factors of the denominators and all their ultimate quotients. This is modern method to find the L.C.M. Mahāvīra also says that the multiplication of the numerators and denominators by the quotient obtained in division of nirudha by

-
6. एकांशकराशीनां द्याद्या रूपोत्तरा भवन्ति हराः । स्वासन्नपराभ्यस्तास्सर्वे दलिताः फले रूपे ॥
 7. सदृशहृदच्छेदहृतौ मिथोऽशहारी समच्छिदावशौ । लुप्तैकहरौ योज्यौ त्याज्यौ वा भागजातिविधौ ॥
 8. छेदापवर्तकानां लब्धानां चाहतो निरुद्ध स्यात् । हरहतनिरुद्धगुणिते हरांशगुणे समो हारः ॥

the denominators makes the denominators equal.

In G.S.S 3-2. Mahāvīra gives the rule for multiplication of fractions and in G.S.S 3-8 he gives the rule for the division of fractions .

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